

EQUATION OF THE DERIVATIVE OF THE FUNCTION TO SOLVE EQUATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7315764>

Abstract. This article presents approximate calculations using the exact integral

Keywords: integral, equality, inequality.

УРАВНЕНИЕ ПРОИЗВОДНОЙ ФУНКЦИИ ДЛЯ РЕШЕНИЯ УРАВНЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены приближенные расчеты с использованием точного интеграла

Ключевые слова: интеграл, равенство, неравенство.

INTRODUCTION

Let us be given a non-standard equation in the form of some kind of $f(x) = 0$ in section $[a, b]$. Let it be required to find the solution of this equation in Section $[a, b]$ (if it exists) ε in accuracy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

First of all, we check whether the function $f(x)$ satisfies the conditions of Baltsano-Cauchy theorem 1 in the section $[a, b]$ or not.

Theorem one of Balsano-Koshi. If the function $f(x)$ is defined on the section $[a, b]$ and is continuous and has different sign value at the extreme points of the interval, then there exists a point $c \in (a, b)$ such that $f(c) = 0$.

So, if the function $f(x)$ fulfills the conditions of the theorem, then the section $[a, b]$ contains the solution of the equation $f(x) = 0$.

RESULTS

Suppose that the section $[a, b]$ contains the root of the equation $f(x) = 0$. That is, let $x \in [a, b]$ exist such that $f(x) = 0$ is equal. Also let $x = a + \Delta x$ be. Then the equality $f(a + \Delta x) = 0$ holds. If we consider the equation $f(x_0 + \Delta x) \approx f(x_0) + f'(x_0) \cdot \Delta x$,

$$f(a + \Delta x) \approx f(a) + f'(a) \cdot \Delta x \approx 0 \text{ equality, that is, } \Delta x \approx -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \text{ is formed. From}$$

this, if we consider the equality $\Delta x = a - x$,

$$x - a \approx -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)}, \quad x \approx a - \frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \text{ equalities are formed.}$$

If the equality $\left| -\frac{f(a)}{f'(a)} \right| < \varepsilon$ is fulfilled, the solution of the equation will be found

approximately with accuracy ε .

Suppose that this inequality does not hold, then we denote $a - \frac{f(a)}{f'(a)}$ by x_1 and consider the equation in the interval $[x_1, b]$. Denote the root of the equation as $x = x_1 + \Delta x$ and calculate $x \approx x_1 - \frac{f(x_1)}{f'(x_1)}$. If we denote it as x_2 and $|x_2 - x_1| < \varepsilon$ then $x_1 + \Delta x$ is the root. Continuing in this way, after a finite step, the inequality $|x_n - x_{n-1}| < \varepsilon$ is satisfied and x_n is taken to be an approximate solution of the given equation around ε .

Example 1. Prove that the equation $f(x) = x^3 - 3x - 6$ has a unique solution in the interval $[2;3]$ and find it with precision 0.001.

DISCUSSION

Solving. $f(x) = x^3 - 3x - 6$ is a function defined on the interval $[2;3]$, continuous and $f(2) = -4 < 0$, $f(3) = 12 > 0$. On the other hand $\forall x \in (2;3)$ for $f'(x) = 3(x^2 - 1) > 0$, that is, the function is increasing. Therefore, the equation $x^3 - 3x - 6 = 0$ has a unique solution in the interval $[2;3]$. Now let's say $x = 2 + \Delta x$ and find Δx such that $f(x) = f(2 + \Delta x) = 0$. For sufficiently small Δx

$$f(2 + \Delta x) = f(2) + \Delta f(2) \approx f(2) + f'(2) \cdot \Delta x.$$

Then we come to the equation $f(2) + f'(2) \cdot \Delta x \approx 0$. By finding $\Delta x \approx -\frac{f(2)}{f'(2)}$ from

this, we find the equation $x = 2 + \Delta x \approx 2 - \frac{f(2)}{f'(2)}$ for the solution. Finally, taking into account

that $f(2) = -4$, $f'(2) = (3x^2 - 3)|_{x=2} = 9$, we find $x \approx x_1 = 2 - \frac{-4}{9} = 2.4$. Using the same reasoning, we find the solution:

$$x_2 = 2.4 - \frac{f(2.4)}{f'(2.4)} = 2.4 - \frac{0.62}{14.28} \approx 2.360, \quad |x_2 - x_1| = 0.40 > 0.001;$$

$$x_3 = 2.360 - \frac{f(2.360)}{f'(2.360)} \approx 2.356, \quad |x_3 - x_2| = 0.004 > 0.001;$$

$$x_4 = 2.356 - \frac{f(2.356)}{f'(2.356)} \approx 2.356, \quad |x_4 - x_3| = 0.000 < 0.001.$$

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the number 2.356 is the solution of the equation with an accuracy of 0.001.

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